

A tale of two diasporas during the 2025 Romanian presidential elections

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Abstract

This study seeks to elucidate the complexities of the heterogeneous diaspora vote in the 2025 Romanian presidential elections through the examination of secondary data from the Romanian Permanent Electoral Authority. The study seeks to identify trends in the voting data, and to analyze these patterns. The study is at the intersection of diaspora studies and electoral studies, using research from both areas. As historical data shows, in presidential elections, the Romanian diaspora has typically voted for change and for other candidates than internal voters. Our research explores the voting patterns of two different Romanian diasporas in the 2025 Romanian presidential elections, focusing on the cleavage based on votes in EU/Schengen+UK vs non-EU/Schengen+UK countries.

Keywords

Romanian diaspora; voting stations; Schengen area; George Simion; Nicușor Dan

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Introduction

In the fall of 2024, the presidential election was cancelled before the second round through the decision of the Constitutional Court of Romania, invoking the manipulation of electoral votes through digital technologies (Romanian Constitutional Court, 2024). The elections were restarted from scratch, including adding new candidates and removing some candidates who participated in 2024, and rescheduled for May 2025. The role of the Romanian diaspora in the 2025 elections was significant as it was perceived to be responsible for placing the extreme right-wing party leader, George Simion, into the second round. Not only that Simion made it to the second round, but he led in the first round with a margin of almost 2 million extra votes (40.96% of the votes) compared with Nicusor Dan, the second placed candidate in the first round who only received 20.99% of the first-round votes. The majority of the diaspora voted for George Simion and AUR (Alliance for the Union of Romanians) in both rounds (60.79% in round 1 and 55.78% in round 2).

There were vocal opinions, expressed in the media, blaming the diaspora - those Romanians who left-fled the country and are not really going to be directly impacted by the changes in Romania - that their vote almost reversed three decades and a half of democratization and Europeanization and throwing Romania back into Russia's arms as during the Cold War (Colibaseanu, 2025; Coman, 2025). There were allegations that George Simion, while running on a sovereign-nationalist movement platform, will take Romania out of the European Union and move it closer to Russia. Blaming the diaspora for Simion's unexpected performance at the presidential elections, means painting the entire diaspora of 6-6.5 million Romanians with a broad brush. This study aims to highlight the nuances of the heterogenous diaspora vote in the 2025 Romanian presidential elections.

Research question and hypothesis

In this paper we will shed some light on the vote of the Romanian diaspora in the 2025 presidential elections, by analyzing secondary sources: the data from the first and second round of votes in the diaspora, available from the Romanian Permanent Electoral Authority (ROAEP). The results have shown that for both the first and second round of the 2025 presidential elections the diaspora, overall, voted for the populist, extreme-right wing candidate, George Simion. This result goes against most of the previous research conducted on how diasporas vote at the global level, and specifically how the Romanian diaspora voted in previous presidential elections.

The guiding question of this study is: Were there (at least) two different Romanian diasporas voting in the 2025 Romanian presidential elections? Our hypothesis is that yes, there were different diasporas which experienced immigration differently and thus had antagonistic expectations vis-à-vis Romania's future. As such, our interrogation is that the cleavage was based on votes taking place in EU/Schengen+UK vs non-EU/Schengen+UK countries. What we aim to do is to uncover patterns in the voting data, interpret these patterns, and develop some research questions to be developed in future research projects. This study sits at the crossroads of diaspora studies and electoral studies, making use of literature from both these subfields.

Background

External voting (or voting through mail, not in person) has a long history which goes back to the Roman Empire (Nyblade et al, 2022: 3). In the United States, Pennsylvania (1813, during the War of 1812, which lasted from 1812-1815) and then Wisconsin (1862, during the Civil War) allowed for absentee voting for servicemen in the military to vote (Ellis et al, 2007; Postal Record, 2024). Even earlier, in December 1775, before the U.S. declared independence from the United Kingdom, the town of Hollis,

New Hampshire, allowed a group of its soldiers to vote in local elections through absentee letters. The idea that a citizen, who is not a member of the military, can vote from overseas was first implemented by New Zealand in 1890, which allowed merchant seafarers to vote from overseas in 1890 (three years later, in 1893, New Zealand will again be the first country in the world to allow all adult women to vote) and every New Zealander registered voter could vote from overseas as early as 1905. We currently have 141 countries and territories which allow for voting from overseas, according to Wellman et al. (2020) based on their Extraterritorial Voting Rights and Restrictions Dataset, 1950-2020:

“Whereas only a handful of countries organized voting for citizens abroad in 1980, most Western European countries had implemented [it] by 1990, followed by North America, South America, and Eastern Europe in 2000. We observe more recent implementation in sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, and the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, with many countries implementing after 2000 in these regions. It is only within the last decade [author’s note: 2011-2020] that the majority of countries in the world have begun to implement diaspora voting.” (Wellman et al., 2020: 911).

As the world became more democratic in the early part of the 21st century, enfranchisement of citizens who have migrated to other countries has become a signal of democratization for many countries wanting to show their democratic credentials to foreign investors and to build economic and political ties with their diasporas overseas (for a more in-depth list of reasons for the expansion of voting from abroad, see Nyblade et al.,2022; Turcu and Urbatsch, 2014).

Figure 1. Diaspora participation in the Romanian presidential elections, 1990-2025.

In Romania, the first time Romanians overseas could vote in the presidential elections was in 1990. Decree-Law no. 92 from March 14, 1990, article 19 stated that: “voting/polling stations should be organized next to the diplomatic and consular offices of Romania, and next to the economic agencies in those countries in which there are no diplomatic and consular offices, for the voters,

diplomats and their families, and those Romanian citizens who find themselves in those countries on the day of the elections. These voting/polling stations are assigned to the Bucharest electoral college.” The number of voting polls increased over time from 121 in 1990 to 751 in 2020 and 965 in 2025. For a brief history of diaspora voting in Romania see Preda, 2023. As more Romanians decided to live outside of Romania (current estimates put the number of the Romanian diaspora at in-between 6 and 6.5 million people), mail-in voting was introduced for the diaspora at the parliamentary elections of December 2016. This increased significantly the participation of the diaspora in the Romanian elections. For example, in 1992 approximately only 45,000 Romanians voted overseas, while in the presidential elections of 2019 almost 1 million Romanians voted overseas, and in 2025 more than 1.6 million voted overseas.

The Romanian diaspora historically voted for change from the political establishment of the Social-Democrat Party, PSD (the continuators of the Communist Party) as in 1996, 2004, 2009, 2014, and 2019, or for stability as in 2000 (in the second round 70% voted for the left-wing PSD candidate, while in the first round 60% voted for the center-right candidates). In 2000, in the second round of the presidential elections, the Romanian voters were faced either with a known leader, Ion Iliescu, former Communist leader and president of PSD, or with Corneliu Vadim-Tudor, an ultra-nationalist leader. The Romanian voters, including the Romanian diaspora, voted for stability and Iliescu. If we agree that Nicusor Dan, former mayor of Bucharest, despite representing a smaller, non-traditional party (USR), was perceived as a politician of the establishment, we could argue that the vote in favor of Simion was in line with all the previous presidential elections except one (2000), as an anti-establishment vote. But there may also be other factors influencing the diaspora vote in 2025 including global trends (a move towards extreme-right wing, populist politicians in many European and other countries) and the previously canceled 2024 presidential election because of the extreme-right wing candidate, Calin Georgescu, being accused of manipulation of the voters via nontransparent technological tools.

Before the presidential election, Romania faced on June 9, 2024 the local and European elections, and on 1st of December 2024 the parliamentary elections. In June 2024, the European Parliament elections showed once again that voters from abroad had been discontented about the parties they voted for in 2019 (Sandu, 2024). The 2024 election results reveal a significant disparity between citizens living abroad and in the country. For instance, only 5% of the diaspora supported the PSD-PNL coalition, in contrast to over 50% of domestic voters.

The examination of the voting trends in Romania and the correlations with migration experiences suggests that the Schengen area acts as a border to support AUR, SOS, REPER, and other extreme right-wing parties, and the Romanian voters from the non-Schengen area inclined towards a more ideological vote, going deeper than a need for change. Moreover, regions with a significant emigration history predominantly supported parties other than the mainstream PSD-PNL coalition, particularly AUR, illustrating a shift from the pro-USR vote to the pro-AUR+SOS vote. The shift from voting an anti-establishment party in 2019 (USR) to the new anti-establishment parties AUR+SOS in 2024, but opposite in the ideological spectrum, reflects the desire for change of Romanian political life and lack of ideological commitment.

Literature review

This study fits within the literature on the voting rights of diaspora communities. In the previous section, we mentioned briefly some of the research conducted about external voting (Nyblade et al, 2022; Ellis et al., 2007; Wellman et al., 2020) and specifically about the history of the political participation of the Romanian diaspora (Preda, 2023). There are two more lines of research which need

to be discussed: research focused specifically on the votes of the Romanian diaspora and research about the larger questions regarding how diasporas vote, in general, at European level (for left-wing or right-wing, for populist-nationalist candidates, for anti-establishment candidates?).

Popescu (2016) presents the legislative changes allowing diaspora to vote from abroad, not just for the presidential elections, but also for the parliamentary elections with the introduction of parliamentary seats for the diaspora (note: from 1990 to the introduction of the 2008 electoral legislation, votes from abroad were counted towards Bucharest's electoral college for the parliamentary elections). The importance of the votes from the Romanian diaspora are highlighted by Popescu by showing that the vote from the diaspora changed the final results in the second round of the 2009 presidential election: The Presidential elections in Romania on November 22, 2009, and December 6, 2009, saw the Democrat-Liberal Party's candidate win the presidency, influenced by 115,831 votes from electors abroad. (Popescu, 2016: 220). His research also highlights some of the administrative (the documents needed by members of the Romanian diaspora to vote) and logistical (distance to voting stations, cost of travel etc.) hurdles faced by members of the Romanian diaspora. Some of these hurdles have been addressed by the Romanian government in recent years with the introduction of the mail-in voting for the diaspora, allowing in-person voting over three days since 2019, and also with the opening of many more voting stations. For example, a study (Comai, 2019) on the 2019 Romanian presidential elections showed a high density of voting stations for the Romanian diaspora in Republic of Moldova, Italy, Belgium, UK, and parts of Spain. In Italy, the average distance to a voting station for the Romanian diaspora was 18 kilometers.

No wonder then that Burean (2011) found that an increase in the number of voting stations leads to higher turnout in the Romanian diaspora. Those findings are still supported almost 15 years later. What is shocking is the sharp increase of the number of voting stations (or the incredibly low number in the 1990s and early 2000s) for the Romanian diaspora from 2 in 2000 in Italy to 160 in 2025, or from 1 in Spain and Republic of Moldova in 2000 to 147, and 64 voting stations in 2025, respectively. Interestingly, in a follow-up study Burean and Popp (2015) argue that there is an "apathetic Romanian diaspora that is absent from elections even if since the 2009 presidential elections the number of voters more than doubled", while acknowledging the increased numbers of voters in the diaspora. Contradicting Burean and Popp's (2015) findings, Vilcu (2014) argued, based on a number of interviews focused on the 2014 elections and which were conducted with Romanians aged 25-40, that "[w]e can say that the Romanian diaspora have proven to have a proactive attitude as opposed to resignation and indifference." It is possible that this conclusion was drawn because of the age of these individuals and also because the 2014 elections in the Romanian diaspora were particularly problematic with long queues of people waiting to vote. There were no such problems in 2025, when the presidential elections were organized very well across the world for the Romanian diaspora, with no long queues and with three days of voting, in addition to the mail-in voting option. Nevertheless, the controversy on this election persists in the public opinion.

Several studies analyzed the factors which influence the divergent vote of diaspora, including the perceptions of democracy, freedom of speech, religion, sexual minority rights, welfare, gender equality, immigration, and living standards between the countries of origin and settlement (Bertelli, 2021). Romanian migrants often offer detailed critiques of Romania's political system, education, and societal tolerance compared to their residence country, favoring the political and social environment, and the greater transparency of the latter. (Bertelli, 2021) However, some Romanians expressed a preference for Romania regarding immigration, citing concerns about everyday nationalism and segregation in their new homeland.

Previous research (Soare and Tufis, 2022; Băluță and Tufis, 2024) has examined ideologies, programmatic features of parties, and mobilization strategies, as well as the preferential links with different societal organizations for recruitment and support (Dinas et al., 2016) to aid voter mobilization, and to internalize party values (Dinas et al. 2016). While most studies focus on national contexts, relevant research has explored transnational movement on left and right, including populist parties (Aslanidis, 2018; Moffitt, 2017), as well as campaigns targeting emigrant communities and their perceived impact on home countries (Jakobson et al., 2021; 2022). This line of inquiry intersects with literature on transnational voting behavior, which suggests non-resident citizens tend towards cosmopolitan, rather than nationalist or populist, attitudes (Turcu and Urbatsch, 2022). Contrary to this interpretation, recent analysis (Soare and Tufis, 2022; Moffitt, 2017) posits that the success of AUR is due to the ability of the party to mobilize migrants interested in maintaining group identity, integrating them into the homeland demos. This is crucial for the promise of defending popular sovereignty by granting natives access to power regardless of their residence. (Bolleyer, 2013). It focuses on the dimension of populism that values ethnic-based transnational connections, and the so-called demos, making place for a new political project that prioritizes migration and mobility. Individual agendas are framed in a more extended ethno-national project, empowering the transnational people in the name of a distinct cultural identity even in different residences.

According to certain comparative studies (Szulecki et al., 2023), the Central and Eastern European diaspora votes often mirror their countries of origin, reflecting a continued connection to homeland party systems. Quantitative data (Szulecki et al., 2023) shows that the diaspora follows trends of the country of origin like populism, nevertheless displays systematic 'distortions' as well. The presidential elections in 2025 in Romania is interpreted as a case of distortion. As such, the Romanian electoral result in the diaspora has deviated from those in the homeland. Romania migrants differ in their voting behavior when compared with the internal voters.

Romanian diaspora

The Romanian diaspora of approximately 6-6.5 million people (Pop, 2023; Stirile ProTV, 2024), is largest within some of the European Union member-states such as Italy (approximately 1.1 million Romanians), Germany (more than 900,000), and Spain (over 620,000, but informally closer to 1 million). Fourth country for the Romanian diaspora, in terms of size, is a former EU member, until 2020, the United Kingdom, with approximately 540,000 Romanians. Outside of the European continent, the largest recipient of Romanians is the United States, with over 425,000 Romanians living there. Canada, Argentina, Austria, Ukraine, and France complete the top 10. The largest recipient countries of Romanians in other world regions which are not in the top 10 include Israel for the Middle East (about 86,000), Australia for Oceania (about 43,000 people of Romanian descent), Kazakhstan for Asia (about 15,000), and South Africa for Africa (about 3,000).

For the 2025 election, it was estimated that a little more than 1 million Romanians in the diaspora had the right to vote. Obviously, the data was wrong as 1.6 million Romanians voted for round 2. If we are to do a basic calculation of the Romanians in the diaspora that have the right to vote, assuming that the percentage of Romanians aged 18 (INS, 2024) or higher, in the diaspora, is similar to that within Romania (82.6%), there should be approximately 4.9 million Romanians with the right to vote in the diaspora. If that is so, then the voting participation of Romanians in the diaspora was of approximately 32.65%, significantly lower than the 64.72% overall for round 2 of the 2025 elections, and 53.21% of round 1 of the same elections providing some support to Burean & Popp (2015) comment about an "apathetic Romanian diaspora". Of course, for Romanians overseas voting is not as

simple as walking down the street to the voting station, but there are several major costly hurdles. This cost is generated by the distance to voting stations (despite the high density in countries in Western Europe and Republic of Moldova), the travel cost (airfare, train, finding someone with an available car), the need to find arrangements for child care or elderly care to go and vote, and finally, the potential lack of appropriate Romanian documents to vote. For example, regarding distance, there are Romanians in southern India, in Kerala, but the only voting station, even in 2025, was in New Delhi, more than 2,600 kilometers away. No wonder then that for the second round of the 2025 presidential election only 53 people voted from the approximately 400 Romanians living in India. The same applies to Argentina, where there are approximately 200,000 Romanians and descendants of Romanians living and only one voting station open in Buenos Aires (66 Romanians voted there in 2025), for a country 12 times larger in size than Romania. Even in Canada, which has the second largest Romanian diaspora in the Americas, in terms of population with over 215,000 Romanians, and is 42 times larger than Romania in size, there were only 13 voting stations open in 2025.

Figure 2. Percentage of voters in the diaspora based on age range.

All of these numbers mentioned above are not meant to criticize the Romanian Ministry of Foreign Affairs which has opened more and more voting stations over the last few Romanian elections than ever before, but to show the need for even more voting stations and/or the need for electoral education of Romanians in the diaspora to help these Romanians use mail-in voting. The use of Romanian churches, schools, and cultural centers, like in 2025, increased the number of voting stations bringing the ability to vote closer to Romanians overseas. When voting polls are nearby, like in Singapore, a city-state three times smaller than Bucharest, which had one voting poll for the Romanian diaspora there were 318 Romanians who voted there in 2025. This number makes us as researchers either assume that most of the Romanians living in Singapore are civically minded and they went to vote or wonder if there are over 1,000 Romanians living in tiny Singapore if we are to use the average

voting participation in the diaspora of approximately 32.65%. We'd argue that it is more likely that the proximity to the voting station (within the same tiny city) is the rationale for such a large participation in Singapore, which placed it third in Asia for the Romanian diaspora's 2025 elections participation after Japan (1,032) and China (883). In other regions of the world, Romanians voted in large numbers in Brazil - 238 votes (largest vote in Latin America) , surprisingly United Arab Emirates - 4134 votes (surprisingly largest vote in the Middle East well ahead of Israel - only 2867 votes, which should have a large Jewish Romanian community), Egypt - 322 votes (largest vote in Africa with only one voting station) and Australia (1943 votes).

Regarding the gender and age distributions overall for the Romanian diaspora participation in the 2025 presidential election, we notice that more men than women voted in round 1 (535,900 vs 437,229 votes or 55% vs 45%) from the total of 973,129 votes cast. For round 2, the gender distribution remained the same with more men voting for women: 885,492 (53.8%) vs 759,966 (46.2%) out of the total of 1,645,458. The only age group in which women voted more than men was in the "65 and over" group, for both rounds (round 1: 29099 women vs 23193 men; and round 2: 47361 women vs 34560 men). The age distribution shows us that most voters came from the 45-64 years old age group with approximately 38.5% on average for the two rounds. Round 2 witnessed an increase in the participation of all the age groups, but with the highest increases for the younger groups (18-24: 78.8% increase; 25-34: 74.9%, and 35-44: 72.1%) as compared with 63.74% increase in the 45-64 age group and 56.66% in the 65 and over age group. This shows to us that younger voters showed up in significantly higher numbers for the second round. One question is if these younger voters voted mostly for Nicusor Dan in the second round, but we do not have data yet to figure out if this is true or not.

Reading the "data leaves"

What patterns can we identify in the data from the two rounds of the 2025 presidential elections? First, George Simion won the overall diaspora vote with 912,806 votes (55.78%) versus Dan's 723,590 (44.22%) votes in the second round, and 587,190 (60.79%) votes versus Dan's 247,388 (25.61%) in the first round. George Simion increased the number of his votes in the diaspora by 55% from the first to the second round, but Nicusor Dan increased his share of the votes in the diaspora by a staggering 192%.

Second, there is a clear cleavage between the vote of Romanians living in EU/Schengen countries (EU+Iceland, Norway) + United Kingdom and outside of the EU/Schengen+UK countries. The UK is included with the EU/Schengen countries in this study because it used to be part of the European Union and it allowed for EU citizens to reside easily in the UK, including Romanian immigrants, until 2020. Simion won only within some of the EU/Schengen+UK countries and lost outside this space. The countries won by Simion include some with the largest numbers of Romanian immigrants like Italy (66.78% of the Romanian diaspora vote for Simion), Spain (67.98%), Germany (68.31%), France (57.21%), and four countries with a smaller Romanian diaspora: Belgium (65.41%), Austria (66.09%), Iceland (53%), and Norway (50.04%). The only non-Schengen country won by Simion was the UK with 58.46%. This means that the Romanian diaspora in the remaining 72 countries in which the vote took place voted majoritarily for the pro-European, pro-democracy candidate, Nicusor Dan.

This is a tale of at least two diasporas: one within EU/Schengen+UK, and one from outside this space. Within EU/Schengen+UK (30 countries total), a large number of Romanians open to nationalist, anti-EU conspiracy theories which were promoted by Călin Georgescu in 2024, and George Simion in 2025, were able to migrate (mostly) legally since Romania joined the European Union in 2007 (there

was a significant pre-2007 Romanian migration to Italy, Spain, UK, and Germany). Many of these migrants were disillusioned with the constant corruption at all levels in Romania and with the lack of hope of returning one day to a better Romania. Living amongst foreigners can, quite often, make migrants more nationalistic (Vertovec, 1999; 2005) and engaged in “long-distance nationalism”, remembering the good old days back home in Romania, missing their family and friends, and rarely overcoming the negative “culture shock” that “things” (with the exception of the salary) were better back home in Romania. Second, quite often these Romanians felt like second class European citizens, doing menial jobs, feeling discriminated against daily in their host country society, in the salary they receive for the unskilled or lower skills work they do, or in housing policies. Thus, once a candidate speaks against the European Union and promises to “clean up” the corrupt Romanian political class “mess”, these ideas resonate amongst many of these members of the Romanian diaspora in EU/Schengen+UK.

But, there is also a different Romanian diaspora within EU/Schengen+UK: the Romanian diaspora which has a middle or higher socio-economic status, has more formal education than the previously mentioned Romanian diaspora, is quite well integrated in the host society, sees daily the benefits of Romania being part of the European Union, and is not willing to bring back to power an extreme right-wing politician which reminded older Romanians of the fascist Iron Guard of the 1930s and early 1940s Romania. This other part of the Romanian diaspora in EU/Schengen+UK is not negligible, but it actually amounts to one third to one-half of the voters in Italy, Spain, Germany, France, UK etc. (the 9 countries won by Simion) and is the majority in the remaining 21 European Schengen countries. When painting the diaspora with a thick brush and blaming it for the support for Simion, it is important to differentiate between the nuances and shades of Romanians ... and Romanians in the diaspora. There are those Romanians who will often go for the conspiracy theories, ultra-nationalist politicians’ ruse, and those Romanians who are more educated, and more politically savvy. These Romanians exist in the diaspora as they exist in Romania, too. This is the EU/Schengen+UK Romanian diaspora which we can see has all kinds of nuances.

The other Romanian diaspora is the one from outside of EU/Schengen+UK. This diaspora lives mostly, based on the voting stations opened for the 2025 elections, in ten countries in the Americas, eleven countries in Africa, eighteen countries in Asia-Oceania, and twelve in Europe outside of the EU/Schengen+UK area. This Romanian diaspora is dominated, in terms of numbers, by those Romanians in the United States and Canada with a combined voting presence of approximately 41,000 people in the second round. This other Romanian diaspora voted overwhelmingly for Nicusor Dan: 68.88% in the U.S., and 68.97% in Canada. Dan won the vote in round 2 in all these countries outside of EU/Schengen+UK.

In the United States, in round 1 Nicusor Dan gained more votes than George Simion in 36 out of the 50 voting stations, and in 47 out of the 50 voting stations in round 2. The voting stations which switched from Simion to Dan in round 2 include Charlotte, four voting stations in the Chicago area and suburbs, Michigan 2, Anaheim, Sacramento, San Antonio, Dacula (Georgia), Ft. Myers, Tampa, Jacksonville, and Queens (New York). Phoenix (Arizona), Portland (Oregon), and Naples (Florida) were the only voting stations which remained in favor of Simion for the second round, too, but with diminished margins in Portland (45 votes for Simion) and Naples (2 votes for Simion).

The voting stations which voted more for the extreme right-wing candidate in round 1 are within North Carolina, Illinois, Michigan, California, Texas, Georgia, Florida, and New York. Five of these states usually vote right-wing politicians in U.S. elections, but when we see that half of the voting stations are in left-leaning states in U.S. elections, it is not possible to make an argument that the

Romanian diaspora in the U.S. voted the way those cities or states usually vote. Instead, a stronger argument is the type of Romanians who live in these cities, with a focus on those which did not change the vote in the second round (Phoenix, Portland, and Naples). Naples is basically one large retirement community in Florida, and we'd expect older people to vote for the ultra-nationalist Simion, while Phoenix is the seat of a large, quite nationalist Romanian diaspora community with a mix of retired people and professionals. For example, a Romanian-American from Phoenix, Ben Toma, Republican, served as the Speaker of the Arizona House of Representatives from 2021-2023. The Romanian diaspora in Phoenix also gave Simion the largest percentage of votes in the second round from all the voting stations outside of the EU/Schengen+UK with 53% of the votes. The only "odd" vote for the extreme-right wing candidate in Romania comes from Portland, Oregon which is perceived in the United States as one of the most progressive (left-wing) cities in the United States. We can only speculate that the Romanian diaspora in Portland was showing a backlash against the left-wing progressiveness of American Portland and thus voted for the extreme right-wing candidate ... in the Romanian presidential elections. On the other hand, the largest pro-Dan vote in the Romanian diaspora in the U.S. was in Wakefield, Massachusetts, one of the suburbs of Boston. This makes sense given the large number of well-integrated professionals from Romania who work in higher education, business, medical and tech companies in and around Boston.

In Canada, despite 6 of the 13 voting stations set up voting more for Simion than for Dan in round 1, all 13 voting stations voted for Dan in round 2. The 6 voting stations which flipped between the two rounds were Calgary, Moncton, New Brunswick; Kitchener, Ontario; Windsor, Ontario; Winnipeg, and Edmonton. The largest pro-Dan round 2 vote was in Toronto, one of the two cities in Canada with the largest Romanian communities (the other one is Montreal). The largest pro-Simion vote, based on the percentage in round 2 was in Kitchener, about 100 miles west of Toronto, in Ontario. Outside of the two largest Romanian diasporas overseas, in the United States and Canada, overall Nicusor Dan did very well, while George Simion did poorly. For example, in Vietnam, 97.7% of the votes cast (85 out of 87) were for Dan. Uzbekistan follows with 97.1% of the votes for Dan, and South Korea is 3rd with 94.66%. Out of the 965 voting stations in the diaspora, Dan won more than 90% of the vote in 35 of these, including two in which probably only the diplomats voted (Turkmenistan 7 votes, all for Dan, and in the capital of Brazil, Brasilia, 7 votes, all for Dan) and he won more than 80% of the votes in 130 of the voting stations. From the voting stations Nicusor Dan won with a difference of more than 1,500 votes in the second round, 28 were in the Republic of Moldova (the largest difference for Dan was 4,929 votes in Chisinau precinct 16), four in Hungary, one in Canada (Toronto), one in UK (London-Tottenham), and one in Switzerland (Zurich).

Unlike Dan, Simion did not win any voting stations with 90% or more of the votes. The only one that came close was in Italy, Corigliano-Rossano, with 89.8% of the votes going to Simion. Simion won with a difference larger than 1,500 votes in 48 voting stations (20 Germany, 8 Italy, 7 UK, 5 Austria, 3 Spain, 3 Belgium, 1 France). The largest difference for Simion against Dan was in London-Harrow 3 with 6,583 votes in his favor. In only 33 voting stations did Simion win more than 80% of the votes (as compared with Dan's 130 voting stations). These stations were in Spain (17), Italy (8), Germany (4), Belgium (2), France (1) and the UK (1). This being said, Simion did win more voting stations in the diaspora for round 2 of the elections: 583 voting stations out of a total of 965.

The participation of the Romanian diaspora increased significantly from round 1 to round 2, thus accounting for some of the voting stations changing from pro-Simion to pro-Dan. For example, in the United States participation increased by 96%, in Canada by 83%, or in Australia by 70%. Within the EU/Schengen+UK there was also increased participation (UK by 70%; Norway by 68%; France by 75%).

There were several voting stations which flipped from Simion to Dan from round 1 to 2 (while none flipped from Dan to Simion in round 2). Minsk, Belarus; Amman, Jordan; Erbil, Iraq; Moscow and St. Petersburg, the only two voting stations in Russia; Varsset and Zajecar in Serbia; Damascus in Syria; Istanbul 1 in Turkey and Cernauti in Ukraine) in addition to the US and Canada voting stations mentioned were the voting stations which flipped from round 1 to 2 for pro-Dan. These are interesting locations with three of them having a historical Romanian presence (the ones in Serbia and Cernauti, Ukraine). One can only assume that those who voted Simion bought into his nationalist anti-EU rhetoric, while those who voted in round 2 for Dan did not vote in round 1 at all, or they voted for someone else than the two finalists.

In the Republic of Moldova, which with 64 voting stations had the largest number of voting stations outside of the EU/Schenghen+UK (and ranked number 6 in the world, after Italy, Spain, UK, Germany, and France), Dan won more votes than Simion in both round 1 and 2. This is an impressive result, showing that the Moldovan-Romanians did not vote for the extreme right-wing candidate, known, before becoming a politician, as the leader of a movement militating for Romania's union with the Republic of Moldova. Voters from the Republic of Moldova currently constitute the largest segment of the diaspora electorate (27%), reflecting a notable shift in the group's demographics and their robust endorsement of the PNL-PSD coalition.

Since 1991, Romania has enabled the reacquisition of citizenship for individuals residing in former territories of former Greater Romania (1918–1940), as well as for those who can demonstrate descent from previous citizens. This has allowed numerous Moldovan residents to regain Romanian citizenship while maintaining their Moldovan citizenship (since 2003) while living in both countries. (Knott, 2016) As a consequence, people become more genuine voters and citizens. This supports findings about why Moldovan citizens vote: Moldovans consider the voting process a duty (Marshall and Bottomore, 1992).

Analysis of votes in specific countries

Now, we should pay attention to the countries which have basically won the vote in the diaspora for Simion in the second round: listing them in the order of smallest difference for Simion to the largest difference for Simion - France (+13,028), UK (+45,358), Spain (+68,156), Italy (+95,448), and Germany (+101,907). The difference in the diaspora for round 2 between Simion and Dan was 189,216 (basically, a little bit less than what Simion won in Italy and Germany combined).

Table 1. Voting in round 2 of the 2025 Romanian presidential election in specific countries.

Country	Simion	% Simion	Dan	% Dan	Δ Simion - Dan
Italy	189891	66.70	94443	33.22	95448
France	51409	57.25	38381	42.75	13028
Germany	190099	68.31	88192	31.69	101907
Spain	128854	67.98	60698	32.02	68156
UK	156701	58.46	111343	41.54	45358
Total	716954		393057		323897

In Italy, Dan won 10 voting stations out of 160. In 9 out of these 10, Dan lost the first round. The only voting station which voted for Dan in Italy in both rounds was Bari 2 where he got 71% of the votes. The 10 voting stations where Dan won more votes than Simion in the second round were: Bari 2, Venice, Milano 1, 2, 3 and 4 (all of the voting stations in Milano), and 4 out of the 7 voting stations in Rome (Rome 1, 2, 3, and 4). The largest difference in favor of Dan was registered in Venice (+577 votes), while the largest difference in favor of Simion was registered in Castelfranco Veneto (+2223 votes), one hour outside Venice by car. The fact that the two communities with the largest victories for the two candidates are so close to each other gives us an indication about how fragmented the Romanian diaspora in Italy is, and that we cannot really differentiate between the votes cast in the north vs. the south of Italy or urban vs rural.

Shockingly, in Germany, Dan won only in 3 out of 88 voting stations (two in Munich, and one in Berlin). In all, Dan won only these three voting stations in the second round, managing to flip them from the first round. Munich 1 with 56.5% was the voting station in which Dan won the highest percentage and margin (+315 votes). Simion won the highest percentages in Rheda-Wiedenbruck (North Rhine-Westfalia) - 84%, Quakenbruck (Lower Saxony) - 82.9%, Essen (Oldenburg) in Lower Saxony - 81.7%, and Sogel in Lower Saxony - 80.5%. Interestingly, Dortmund and Duisburg had the highest margins of victory in favor of Simion with +3514 and +3232 votes. The large losses of Dan in Germany, and the gains of the extreme right-wing candidate in Germany should give food for thought for political marketing specialists in Romania. In Germany, the only pattern noticeable is that the diaspora in two of the three most populous cities (Berlin and Munich) voted for Dan.

In France, Dan won 21 voting stations out of 68 (note: in addition, Dan also won, in both rounds, the voting station in the Principality of Monaco, where a surprisingly high number of Romanians voted - 716) in the second round. There were only 7 voting stations in France which voted for Dan in both rounds: Issy-Les-Moulineaux (suburb of Paris), Colmar (the tourist destination in the Alps), and all the voting stations in Paris (Paris 1,2,3, 4, and 5). In addition, Dan was able to flip from the first to the second round, the following voting stations: Rueil-Malmaison (suburb of Paris), Strasbourg 1, Clermont-Ferrand, Antibes, Lyon 1 and 2, Nice 1 and 2, Troyes, Saran (suburb of Orleans), Caen, Montreuil 2 (suburb of Paris), Beauvais, and Tours. The best results obtained by Dan were in the five voting stations in Paris (in-between 71.8% and 79.3%). The best result obtained by Simion was in Calais with 83.3%, followed by La Courneuve (suburb of Paris), Bastia in Corsica, and Loudeac in Brittany. Except for La Courneuve, a poor suburb of Paris, Dan won Paris (Paris 1 with an advantage of 1,361 votes) and most of its suburbs, as well as in the larger cities like Lyon, and in touristic locations (Colmar, Nice, Antibes). Simion won cities like Nantes (+1517) and La Courneuve (+1329) but also in cities such as Toulouse, Rennes, Bordeaux, Brest, Lille, Marseille, Ajaccio, Bastia, Dijon, Montpellier.

In Spain, Dan won in 17 out of the 147 voting stations for round 2. In 6 of these, Dan was able to gain more votes than Simion in round 1, too: Barcelona 2 and 3, Madrid 5, Adeje in Gran Canaria, Santa Cruz de Tenerife, and Sevilla 2. Dan was able to flip 11 voting stations from round 1 to round 2: Marbella, Malaga 1 and 2, Valencia 1 and 2, Madrid 1 and 2, Barcelona 1, 2, and 3, Maspalomas in Gran Canaria, Manilva (south of Malaga), and Las Palmas in Gran Canaria. The largest percentage victory for Dan was in Barcelona 3 with 79.9% of the votes in his favor, while the largest quantity victory was in Barcelona 2 with +862 votes for Dan. Simion won more than 80% of the votes in 17 voting stations with Almendralejo (Extremadura), Almonte (Andalucia), and Moguer (Andalucia) leading the charts. When it comes to votes, Simion won with the largest difference in Lleida (Catalunya) with Lleida 2 (+1889) and Lleida 1 (+1779). In Spain, the pattern which emerges shows a pro-Dan vote in the most

populous cities of Madrid, Barcelona, and Valencia, and Sevilla and in the touristic towns of Marbella, Manilva, and in the Canary Islands.

Finally, in the country outside of the EU/Schengen that has the largest Romanian diaspora community, in the United Kingdom, Dan won in 34 out of 108 voting stations for round 2. In 11 of these Dan was able to gain more votes than Simion in round 1, too: London - Tottenham Court Road, Westminster 1 and 2, Greenwich, Richmond, Southwark, White City, Wandsworth; Cambridge; Edinburgh 1 and 2. Some of the cities flipped by Dan from the first to the second round include: Oxford, Aberdeen, Bournemouth, Sheffield, Manchester, Portsmouth, Exeter etc. Dan won in London-Tottenham Court Road with 87.5% and with the largest margin of +2,096 votes. Simion had the largest victory in London-Harrow 3 with 83% of the vote, where he also had his largest margin with +6,583. In addition to winning 23 London voting stations (to Dan's 11 London voting stations) Simion also won in cities such as Ipswich, Liverpool, Nottingham, or Newcastle.

The patterns we can notice in these five countries is that the Romanian diaspora:

- a) in Germany was heavily in favor of Simion,
- b) in Italy was very fragmented in its vote with no discernable patterns,
- c) in the UK, France and Spain the pro-Dan vote was in the larger cities (London, Manchester, Paris, Lyon, Madrid, Barcelona, Valencia, and Sevilla) plus touristic locations (Bournemouth, Colmar, Nice, Antibes, Marbella, Manilva, Canary Islands), and cities with large universities (Oxford) voted for Dan and for Europe.

More research is needed about the several Romanian diasporas and the way they vote in Romanian elections. First, a voting polls density in all the countries should be created, to get a sense of the easiness of voting for Romanians in the diaspora. Second, data on the background (year of immigration, education levels, an assessment of integration into the host society, socio-economic indicators, family still living in Romania) on the voters pro-Dan and pro-Simion should be gathered. We expect that all these indicators impact the voting choices of Romanians overseas.

Conclusion

Our analysis has shown that the 2024 diaspora vote has been marked by discontent and fragmentation. The diaspora electorate is regarded as split in its presidential vote with voters from outside of the EU/Schengen+UK area supporting the pro-EU candidate, while those Romanian voters from the EU/Schengen+UK aligning mostly with the extreme-right wing party candidate (Simion). But even within the Romanian voters from the EU/Schengen+UK area, the extreme-right wing candidate won only in 9 out of the 30 countries, albeit these were the countries with the highest number of Romanian immigrants. Even within the 5 largest countries for the Romanian diaspora (Italy, France, Germany, Spain, UK) which voted for the extreme-right wing candidate, and against stability, those Romanians in the larger cities, touristic and educational towns, voted for stability and the pro-EU path. Thus, we conclude that by "reading the voting data leaves" we can identify at least four different diasporas: a clear cleavage EU/Schengen+UK (1) vs the rest of the world (2), and within the EU/Schengen+UK there are: 21 countries in which the Romanian diaspora voted for the EU (3), 9 countries in which the votes went mostly to the extreme right-wing, but within these 9 countries the largest cities, touristic and educational towns voted for the pro-EU candidate.

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